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ANCIENT THEORY OF HUMAN BODY CHANNELS

AUTHORS

1. Pankaj Kumar Jain, Lecturer, Department Of Sharir Kriya, State Model Ayurved College (SMIAS), Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India.

Abstract:

Srotas are the specified and communicative transportation channels found in human body as well other organism also. Srotas formed fundamental and structural path to flow different material. Srotas are describe in Ayurvedic texts in very detail but that is not make easy understanding for ayurvedic scholar as well as for non-ayurvedic person. So the aim of present article is explain the Srotas theory in simple view with different aspects.

For Corresponds:

Name of Author: Dr. Pankaj Kumar
Jain
Email: pj@drpankajjain.com

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Introduction:

Ayurveda is a life science and life is continuity of Dhatu. Dhatu is Ayurvedic understanding about metabolism are going around or including Dhatu Utpatti, Dhatu Sthiti and Dhatu Laya.

Dhatu Utpatti is process of tissue formation, start in intrauterine life. This is the process of differentiation. A single cell is divided and forms a multi-cellular organism. Groups of similar cell called tissue and growth of these tissues are also including in Dhatu Utpatti. Maintaining the the tissue is including in Sthiti and Laya is destroying process of the old cells via apoptosis.

Srotas may be visible viz. Sthoola Srotas or invisible viz. Sukhma Srotas. They are the communication channel between the organ involve in Dhatu Niraman Prampara or whole body metabolism.

Ayan Mukh (opening) and Ayan (passage) both are including in Srotas. Only input and output channels are having outer openings. Some other outer openings are known as Bahi Srotas. According to Shrusht nine Bahi Srotas (external openings) are present in male and 12 in female¹.

Shrusht told mostly anatomical aspect of Srotas. So he could not included Asthivaha, Majjavaha and Svedavaha Srotas in counting of Ekadash Yugma Srotas (11 pairs of Srotas).¹²

मूलमिति प्रभवस्थानम् (Chakrapani on Ch. Vi. 5/8)³

These flow channel or Srotas are communicating the organs to each other which are involved in metabolism. Thirteen main big internal channels are present in our body according Charak. That all can be divided in three groups viz.

1. Input system flow channel
2. Transforming channel
3. Output system flow channel

1. Input system flow channel:

Srotas are involve in Dhatu Utpatti are known as input system flow channel. three main Srotas Udayavaha, Annavaha and Pranvaha are engage in providing raw material for formation and maintain the Dhatu.

भावविशेषा इति उत्पत्तिमन्तो विशेषाः (ch. Vi.5/3)⁴

Nutrient are use as a fuel for the propose of formation and maintain the Dhatu. Continues supply of nutrients is very important. Nutrient are mostly found in diet and diet is divided in two streams like solute (Anna) and solvent (Udak). Combination of Anna and Udak are known as diet. Important work of solvent is increasing availability for absorpation to tissue.

Energy is fundamental need for body functioning. Oxygen is also important for energy production in human being.

Pranvaha Srotas is oxygenated air transporting system work on gross and minuet level. Root organ of this system described Hridaya and MahaSrotas.

हृदयशब्देनात्र हृदयोपलक्षितः प्रदेश उच्यते, न तु साक्षाद् हृदयं; (Dalhana, Su.Su.14/3)⁵

Thus, it is inferred that the root of Pranavaha Srotas is not only the releted to heart, but also also cover the whole thorex.

प्राणवहानामिति प्राणसञ्ज्ञकवातवहानाम्, एतच्च प्राणाख्यविशिष्टस्य वायोर्विशिष्टस्रोतः (Chakrapani on Ch. Vi. 5/8)⁶

Disturbing factor of pranvaha shrots are Khasya (deficiency), Vega Sandharan (not avoid natural urge timely), Rokshaya, Vyayam (excessive exercise)

भवन्ति चात्र- क्षयात् सन्धारणाद्रौक्ष्याद्यायामात् क्षुधितस्य च प्राणवाहीनि दुष्यन्ति स्रोतांस्यन्यैश्च दारुणैः (Ch. Vi. 5/10)⁷

Khasya (deficiency) is mainly circulaatory disturbing cause of Pranvaha Srotas due to less oxygen binding cpapsity.

Vega Sandharan (not avoid natural urge timely) is nural couse. It easily understand with the example of urea, when serum urea level become high the respiratory symptum are produced.

Rokshayat is gorup of local factor of Pranvaha Srotas involment of Alveolar fluid and surfactant deffect by distube function of type II Alveolar cells.

Excessive exercise is damaging factor due to severe hyperactive work cross the limit parameters.

Fundamental description of airway pathology according to Charak. The symptoms like अतिसृष्ट (excessive) अतिबद्धं (Obstructed) कुपित (agitated) अल्प (Shallow) अनल्प (Fast) सशब्द (wheezing and all other respiratory sounds) सशूलमुच्छसन्तं (Dyspnoea-painful breathing) are all accounted as cardinal symptoms of resiratory diseases.

तद्यथा- अतिसृष्टमतिबद्धं कुपितमल्पाल्पमभीक्षणं वा सशब्दशूलमुच्छसन्तं दृष्ट्वा प्राणवहान्यस्य स्रोतांसि प्रदुष्टानीति विद्यात् (Ch. Vi. 5/7)⁸

Annvaha srotas is correlated with upper part of gastro intestinal tract. Main functions of this Srotas are supply row material, converting it as absorbable form (digestion).

अन्नवहानां स्रोतसामामाशयो मूलं वामं च पार्श्वं (Ch. Vi. 5/8)⁹

Root organ or origin and destination organ (Mool) of Annvaha Srotas is Amamashaya (esophageal and gastric part of GIT) and Vamparsve (lateral part of stomach and some part of duodenum)

Udakvaha is correlated with supply and management system of solvent, like thirst mechanism. Liquid part of GIT is mostly providing by the saliva, gastric, bile, pancreatic juice, enteric secretion and diet.

उदकवहानां स्रोतसां तालुमूलं क्लोम च (Ch. Vi. 5/8)¹⁰

If input system flow channel are working properly than other system also working well and if disturbed also disturb formation and maintaining system of Dhatu in the level of row material supply.

2. Transforming channel

After the input system absorb nutrients and water in the GIT and oxygenated air in lungs then and transformation take place, and seven phasea of gradual transformation are complete at tissues level. Transforming channel flow the transforming Dhatu. It also provides the site for transformations.

First phase of transformation convert Ahar Rasa into Rasa Dhatu. Transformation of Ras Dhatu into Rakta Dhatu is second phase.

Srotas as it is pave the way for RBC formation by providing amino acids, iron etc. to the liver as well as other body organs.

All cells of different tissues select the required nutrients from the circulating plasma and this selection is according to the eclipse power of the self.

स्रोतांसि खलु परिणाममापद्यमानानां धातूनामभिवाहीनि भवन्त्ययनार्थेन।।(Ch. Vi. 5/3)¹¹

परिणाममापद्यमानानामिति पूर्वपूर्वरसादिरूपतापरित्यागेनोत्तरोत्तररक्तादिरूपतामापद्यमानानाम्। (chakrapani on Ch. Vi. 5/3)¹²

रसवहानां स्रोतसां हृदयं मूलं दश च धमन्यः, शोणितवहानां स्रोतसां यकृन्मूलं प्लीहा च, मांसवहानां च स्रोतसां स्नायुर्मूलं त्वक् च। मेदोवहानां स्रोतसां वृक्कौ मूलं वपावहनं च, अस्थिवहानां स्रोतसां मेदो मूलं जघनं च, मज्जवहानां स्रोतसामस्थीनि मूलं सन्धयश्च। शुक्रवहानां स्रोतसां वृषणौ मूलं शेफश्च (Ch. Vi. 5/8)¹³

Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Mamsavaha, Medovaha, Asthivaha, Majjavaha Shukravaha Srotas is a flow channel for liquid form of Dhatu or internal flow system of row material

3. Output system flow channel are

Three output system flow channel are Mutravaha, Purishvaha and Swedvaha Srotas.

मूत्रवहानां स्रोतसां बस्तिर्मूलं वङ्कणौ (Ch. Vi. 5/8)¹⁴

Mutravaha Srotas is the major way to eliminate of metabolic wastes. organs related to Mutravaha Srotas are Basti and Vanshans.

पुरीषवहानां स्रोतसां पक्काशयो मूलं स्थूलगुदं (Ch. Vi. 5/8)¹⁵

Purishvaha Srotas is opposite site of Annavaha Srotas and their functions eliminate the dietary wastes. Root organ of Purishvaha Srotas are large intestine to anus.

स्वेदवहानां स्रोतसां मेदो मूलं लोमकूपाश्च (Ch. Vi. 5/8)¹⁶

Swedvaha system is heat regulation system and its regulate internal organ temperature and work as cooling pad. Main organ is adipose tissue of skin and hair follicles.

Difference between Input, Transforming, Output flow channel:

Sr.no.	Character	Input system flow channel	Transforming channel	Output system flow channel
1	External opening	Yes, they have external opening	Not open in outside (exception only Shukravaha in male)	They have external opening
2	Flow direction	Flow inside	Circulation	Flow outside the body

Conclusion

A single channel can be load with flowing two or more material, then it will be known as different name, the name was given according their flowing substance. Different parts of GIT are known as Annavaha, Udakavaha and Purishvaha Srotas.

Srotas are participating in production, maintaenc and transport of Dhatu. When Acharya Charak explains the origins of Sources, then the first root of that source speaks about the origins and the transit from other origin.

So the Srotas theory is giving a better understanding of ancient metabolic theories as Uttapati, Sthith and laya. This theory also important to explain the pathogenesis because the K-vegonyat of Srotas is basic feature of Dosh Dhatu Samurchana.

REFERENCES:

1. Shastri Ambikadutta, Susruta Samhita part-1, reprint editon 2006, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Sharir Stahn, 5/10, p-42
2. Chakrvati Haranchndra, Susruta Samhita Part-2, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Sharir Stahn, 9/12, p-126
3. Singh Ramharsh, Carak Samhita Ayurveda Depika, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Chakrapani's comment on Shrotas Vimanam-5/3, p-525
4. The Carak Samahita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-5/3, p-804
5. Chakrvati Haranchndra, Susruta Samhita Part-1, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Dalhan Comment Sutra Sthan, 14/3, p-137
6. Singh Ramharsh, Carak Samhita Ayurveda Depika, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Chakrapani's comment on Shrotas Vimanam-5/3, p-525
7. The Carak Samhita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-05/10, p-814
8. The Carak Samhita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-05/07, p-807
9. The Carak Samhita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-05/08, p-808
10. The Carak Samhita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-05/08, p-808
11. The Carak Samhita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-05/03, p-804
12. Singh Ramharsh, Carak Samhita ayurveda depika, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, Varanasi, Chakrapani's comment on Shrotas Vimanam-5/3, p-524
13. The Carak Samhita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-05/08, p-808
14. The Carak Samhita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-05/08, p-809
15. The Carak Samhita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-05/08, p-810
16. The Carak Samhita Volume IInd, Chaukhamba Orientalia, Varanasi; Viman Sthaana ,Shrotas Vimanam-05/08, p-810

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